

Cybersecurity of Dutch online stores

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ABSTRACT

While the whole world is focused on fighting and minimizing the spread of COVID-19, the number of cyberattacks and threats rose exponentially. With the growing number of cyberattacks and threats, the importance of data security also grew. This research is focused on the cybersecurity of Dutch online stores and machine learning. Through archival research and a survey study, this paper examines the impact of cybersecurity on digital resilience of Dutch online stores and a way of implementing machine learning to improve cybersecurity. This study suggests that machine learning can be used to improve the cybersecurity and that cybersecurity has a positive effect on digital resilience of Dutch online stores.

Keywords

Cybersecurity, Cyber Attack, Machine Learning, Cyber security risks, Digital Resilience

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic affected us all in a certain way. Companies from across the world were forced to handle business in a different way. It became clear that doing business online was needed to survive. Companies got to work with more data. This comes with responsibilities. Not every company is aware of the effects of cyber threats, for example that online stores are less digital resilient and more vulnerable. It becomes more important to do something against cyberattacks, since cyber threats occur more frequently nowadays. To be prepared for a cyberattack every company needs access to the information about cybersecurity and needs the knowledge how to use it. Cyberattacks can cause problems for companies, for example data breaches, espionage and frauds. Since these problems can have a negative influence on a company, cybersecurity has to be taken seriously.

In today's rapidly changing environment, companies have to make difficult decisions about cybersecurity. Decisions are often about opportunities, risks and security. It also looks like

there is a need to detect cyber threats as soon as possible. As a company, it looks like a practical approach to reduce risks and managing cybersecurity is needed.

The focus of this paper will lie on how cybersecurity of online stores impact the digital resilience of an online store and how machine learning can be implemented in the most effective way so that online stores can use it to improve their cybersecurity. Regarding this, this paper will also discuss to what extent cybersecurity is implemented in organizations in combination with machine learning. There is already research available which covers that machine learning and cybersecurity are an effective combination in theory. This research is about how the combination is used in practice and how to do it effectively. In case of a cyberthreat, the results of this research will possibly be helpful for online stores to detect cyberthreats better and handle them more effectively. Every online store is different, so the approach to a data breach will differ from each other. At last, more advantages can be created for online stores, for example more customer confidence and better protection of intellectual property, because of the improved cyber security. This research helps online stores to (better) implement machine learning in cybersecurity.

This paper is structured as follows. After this introduction, there will be eight sections. The first section presents the problem statement. In this paragraph, the problem will be explained in detail. The second section presents the research question. The third section presents the theory used in this paper. The last five sections present the conceptual model, methodology, results, discussion and conclusion.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

This paper is about online stores and their cybersecurity. An online store is a website or application on which goods or services are sold over the internet. These online stores collect personal data of their customers, this data is very valuable for hackers and online stores. It is valuable for online stores for their market design mechanism to fit their site to each customers' personal interests, targeted

advertising, and get insight of customers' behavior (Christl et al., 2017). Hackers find the personal data valuable, because if they have data from the customer which the customer wants to keep secret, they can blackmail the customer. This personal data can be accessible for hackers since this data flows over the internet. With the accessibility of this data, cybersecurity comes around.

The lifecycle of security spans over three processes: prevention, detection and reaction (Apruzzese et al., 2022). Prevention of any cyber threat is an impossible task, whereas the reaction phase assumes that the damage has already taken place (Apruzzese et al., 2022). This research is mainly focused on the detection process in which machine learning is used to detect threats. This study also gives insight on the prevention process with machine learning. At last, this research gives insights on aligning machine learning with cybersecurity effectively.

The impact of a cyberattack can be divided into three categories: financial, reputational and legal (Couce-Vieira et al., 2020). Cyberattacks may affect the company's income, because of loss of sales, contracts, market share or funding. It may also lead to a loss in competitive advantage because of leaked or publicly disclosed sensitive information, including intellectual property or commercial secrets. The reputational damage is based on the customers' or stakeholders' trust in the company, this can lead to a financial effect because of the loss in sales (Couce-Vieira et al., 2020). Cyberattacks possibly can lead to a leak of personal data from customers or employees. If this data is compromised, it means the company has failed to deploy appropriate security measures. This can lead to fines and regulatory sanctions (Héroux & Fortin, 2020). These examples of legal effects especially have an effect on online stores, because they deal with personal data on a large scale. The effects a cyber attack can have underlines the importance of this research, because the effects of a cyber attack can harm both people and companies.

Being resilient as an online store plays a bigger role in the COVID-19 pandemic, since there were more cyber attacks (Chigada & Madzinga, 2021). During the pandemic, people started buying more from home, which meant that the online stores got more data from customers and had to deal with more money transactions (Chigada & Madzinga, 2021). Online shopping is a known way for hackers to collect data. 'Bank loans scams spread rapidly at the peak of the COVID-19 crisis, as many of the scams focused on defrauding people of their money and personal information through online shopping' (Alawida et al., 2022).

This research is conducted on online stores, because nowadays more online stores arise and there are more hackers on the lure (Chigada & Madzinga, 2021). Looking forward, more goods and services will be sold over the internet. Previous research on machine learning and cybersecurity, such as Apruzzese et al.(2022) focuses on the benefits, problems and future challenges of machine learning in the domain of cybersecurity. This paper focuses on the value of machine learning for online stores and how it can improve their cybersecurity. For online stores it is valuable to get an insight on how machine learning can be used.

RESEARCH QUESTION

This research aims to examine the following research question: *How does cyber security impact digital resilience of Dutch online stores and how can machine learning be implemented in the most effective way that online stores can use it to improve their cybersecurity?*

Theoretical sub questions:

1. What is cybersecurity?
2. What is a cyberattack and what is digital resilience?
3. What is machine learning?

Practical sub questions:

4. How can machine learning help cybersecurity to improve?
5. How can machine learning be implemented in an online stores' business process?

THEORY

Cybersecurity

According to different studies, cybersecurity has a broad definition. Cybersecurity can be defined as "the organization and collection of resources, processes, and structures used to protect cyberspace and cyberspace-enabled systems from occurrences that misalign de jure from de facto property rights". (Craig et al., 1970). Cybersecurity can be obtained through systematic developments, by applying software engineering systems with the awareness of the risks and security issues that come with these developments (Kemmerer, 2003). Cybersecurity is a global phenomenon representing a complex challenge for companies. The internet is considered as a safe environment for sharing information, transactions and controlling the physical world.

Cyberattack & Digital resilience

A cyberattack is an action that attempts to bypass security mechanisms of computer systems, a cyber threat is the probability that an attack may occur (Raiyn, 2014). If an online store is affected by a

cyberattack, they need to recover from it. The speed and ability of recovering from a cyberattack shows how resilient the online store is. If online stores are able to recover fast from a cyberattack, this means that they are resilient. This is called digital resilience. Digital resilience is enabling an IT environment that is safe, secure and managed against disruptions (Dr. May Wang, 2022). This could either be recognized through digital online activities or supporting IT infrastructure against cyberattacks. If an online store has an IT environment that can manage a cyberattack well and have little damage from it, the online store can be called resilient.

Machine learning

Machine learning is an evolving branch of computational algorithms that are designed to imitate human intelligence by learning from the surrounding environment. There are four types of machine learning algorithms: supervised, semi-supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement.

In supervised learning, the machine is taught by example. The operator provides the machine learning algorithm with a known dataset that includes inputs and outputs, and the algorithm has to find a method to determine how to arrive at those inputs and outputs. The operator knows the correct answers to the problem, while the algorithm identifies patterns in data, learns from observations and makes predictions. The algorithm makes predictions and is corrected by the operator, this process continues until the algorithm achieves a high level of accuracy and performance. Examples of supervised learning are:

- Regression
- Decision Tree
- Random Forest
- KNN
- Logistic regression

Semi-supervised learning is similar to supervised learning, but instead this method uses both labeled and unlabeled data. Labeled data is essentially information that has meaningful tags so that the algorithm can understand the data, whilst unlabeled data does not have that information.

Unsupervised machine learning studies data to identify patterns. There is no answer key or human operator to provide instruction. Instead, the machine determines the correlations and relationships by analyzing available data. In an unsupervised learning process, the machine learning algorithm is left to interpret large data sets and address that data accordingly. The algorithm tries to organize that data in some way to describe its structure. Examples are:

- K-means clustering

- Principal Component Clustering
- Hierarchical Clustering

Reinforcement learning focuses on systematic learning processes, where a machine learning algorithm is provided with a set of actions, parameters and end values. By defining the rules, the machine learning algorithm then tries to explore different options and possibilities, monitoring and evaluating each result to determine which one is optimal. Reinforcement learning teaches the machine trial and error. It learns from past experiences and begins to adapt its approach in response to the situation to achieve the best possible result. (Mousavi et al., 1970)

Conceptual model

This research aims to understand the influence of machine learning on cyber security and how this correlates with digital resilience. In this study machine learning is the independent variable, cyber security is the mediator and digital resilience is the dependent variable.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated to get a grip on the relationship between the variables in the conceptual model:

H1: Machine learning helps cyber security to improve.

H2: Cyber security has a positive effect on digital resilience

METHODOLOGY

The research in this paper is based on data-collection methods. The data-collection methods are qualitative and quantitative, namely interviews, a survey via Microsoft Forms and desk research. The use of qualitative research is beneficial for this paper, because the research gives a deeper understanding in cybersecurity, the different machine learning methods and how online stores deal with machine learning. The use of quantitative research is beneficial for this paper, because the more data is collected, the better the comparison between different online stores. This will increase the external validity of this research. The survey will be reliable, because the same aspects will be asked in the same way for every participant. The survey will be cross-sectional and multi-item measured. Another reason why a survey is chosen, is to analyze trends and it can be filled in anonymously. As a result, the theoretical framework will be more

worked out, so this paper possibly gives more insights in how cybersecurity could be improved.

The data collected from the desk research are based on academic literature. The academic literature in this case are articles about cybersecurity in general and similar research in cybersecurity. To ensure the quality of the data in this paper, multiple articles are read and compared so that information given in this paper is reliable and valuable. This research is more inductive from nature. The aim of this research is to develop a theory that can possibly help online stores to handle their cybersecurity more effectively in combination with machine learning.

The interviews are semi-structured interviews. Cybersecurity experts are interviewed to get an insight in the knowledge that a team behind the online store has with regard to cybersecurity and how machine learning is helping them to improve their cybersecurity. The interviews help to get an idea of where possibly they need to get more knowledge about cybersecurity and how machine learning has to be more aligned with the processes of the online store. There will be 10 interviews with companies with an online store.

The survey is sent to online stores to get an insight in the way they deal with cybersecurity. With this survey, more information about cybersecurity will be gained and where the knowledge of online stores needs to be improved. To determine whether an online store needs to improve their cybersecurity or not, an evaluation will take place. In this evaluation, there will be a closer look into which precautions online stores already take and which they don't take in case of a cyberattack. There will also be a close look into how online stores possibly can improve their existing precautions. In total, the survey will be sent to 50 companies with an online store.

The desk research gains an insight in the latest news about cyber security and machine learning, similar research and studies related to cyber security. This insight is used to develop a theoretical framework that could be used by online stores to handle their cybersecurity more effectively.

All the data that is collected, will be analyzed with Google Forms. Google Forms gives a clear view of the responses that allows us to make useful conclusions.

This methodology is written to get an insight on which and why certain methods are used to get an insight in cybersecurity. It also gives an insight in theory about machine learning and how it can be aligned with cybersecurity and why the theory could possibly be effective on online stores. At last, there will be a better insight in the relationship between

theory and the real world. (Belaissaoui et al.)

RESULTS

After reviewing multiple online stores by interviewing them and sending a survey on their current knowledge on cybersecurity, it can be concluded that many online stores lack the knowledge about cybersecurity and do not know how to react to cyberattacks. It can also be stated that online stores are aware of the importance of cybersecurity, but there is a lack of knowledge of how to properly implement the right tools in their processes. After reviewing one of the online stores, they did not know who had access to their database. The results show that a lot of online stores show lack of interest in cybersecurity. Also the right policies and knowledge about machine learning is unknown to them. Their main focus is growing in their specific market segment, but are not aware of what responsibilities come with growing.

The results from the desk research are as follows. Cybersecurity in combination with machine learning, is new. There is already research done about the benefits of the combination of machine learning and cyber security, but in real life it is still in an early stage. There is a significant discrepancy between theory and practice. The theory states that machine learning helps cybersecurity to improve. These improvements are mostly related to the speed of detection of intrusions and the speed of reaction to a known attack. The improvements are that machine learning techniques can bring down any security breach with the help of machine learning algorithms. The responsible authorities are informed within a fraction of second about the events. Fraud detection and prevention becomes very easy through machine learning. Big data analysis is possible with various machine learning techniques and with the analysis, doubtful behavior can be brought to the attention of authorities and those can be cured. Instead of totally relying on humans, the detection and prevention is done by machines. The streaming data can be analyzed on the go and fraudulent signal patterns can be pointed out.

Because machine learning and cybersecurity combined is relatively new, there are also some challenges and uncertainties. This is why no online store has implemented machine learning with cybersecurity. First of all, machine learning requires a large amount of data to make models and predictions more accurate. Gaining malware samples is a lot harder than acquiring data from anywhere else. There is not enough attack data and a lot of security risk data is sensitive and not available, because of privacy concerns. Without representative data, the machine learning methods do not work.

The second challenge is that there are much higher accuracy requirements. Every day, organizations see large volumes of data packets cross the firewalls. Even if only one percent of the data is mis-judged by machine learning, huge amounts of normal traffic can be blocked wrong and severely impact the business. It takes time, and it also takes huge amounts of data to actually train a machine learning model to get up to the same level of accuracy as a really skilled human.

The third challenge is the security of machine learning itself. Because of the critical role cybersecurity plays in each business, it is more critical to make sure the machine learning software in cybersecurity is secure by itself.

The fourth challenge is that modern systems are continuously developing: new devices, services, and even users, are added or removed all the time. All such mutations contrast the assumption, preventing the reliable application of machine learning in the long term because the training data quickly becomes outdated. (Nazar Waheed University of Technology Sydney et al., 2021)

DISCUSSION

In the results part it can be concluded that machine learning has a positive effect on cybersecurity. It looks like cybersecurity significantly improves. After doing interviews and surveys, it shows that online stores need to improve their knowledge of machine learning, and what kind of positive impact it can have on their cybersecurity. In this part of the research, we show how to implement machine learning with cybersecurity in an effective way. As a result of this, online stores are better prepared in case of a cyberattack.

The IT department needs to be educated in machine learning in order to improve their cybersecurity in their online stores. The second option is that the company can outsource the part of machine learning to an external company. To analyze which option is useful for the company, they must analyze the costs of internal education or external outsourcing. Each company can have their own preferences, since both of the options will be useful to excel in the innovation of machine learning.

To implement machine learning in cybersecurity in their online stores, it looks like reinforcement learning is the most effective way of machine learning. To implement this kind of machine learning, it is necessary to download the right software program, have a database without incomplete information and develop the most

suitable parameters, so that machine learning can be used in an optimal way. Examples of software programs are Shogun, TensorFlow and Apache Spark MLlib (Team, 2021). In order to prevent threats of the software programs, it is significant to apply the right software security measures that are secured. It is also needed to adjust the right security policies so that not only the data becomes more secure but the machine learning software and applications also.

According to the theory, cyberattacks are a threat to online stores. Cyberattacks can cause major problems. This is the main reason why cybersecurity is important. Without cybersecurity, online stores cannot focus on their core business. This means that an online store without proper cybersecurity, cannot keep up with the fast changing environment. It can be concluded that cybersecurity is essential to keep an online store digital resilient.

Existing research is conducted on the benefits of machine learning in combination with cyber security. Where the theory is described in academic papers, no research has been done on the implementation of machine learning for security. The theory states that machine learning helps cybersecurity to improve, but it has to come clear if this is also the conclusion of the practical way. Therefore, this paper gives insights on closing this knowledge gap by describing a way of effectively implementing machine learning for security

CONCLUSION

Our research shows that cybersecurity is getting more known by companies with an online store and it is acknowledged that taking measurements against cyberthreats is essential. COVID-19 resulted in a growth of awareness against these crimes due to a lot of cyberattacks during the pandemic. However, this did not result in prioritizing the cybersecurity measurements, companies focus on market growth and other aspects rather than investing or hiring a specialist.

The reliability of this research is high, because the answers out of the interviews and survey gave us an useful insight into the different challenges of companies regarding machine learning and cybersecurity. In combination with desk research, the research question could be answered.

Our research could be improved by taking a more generalizable research sample. Our sampling method is too specific and it is not generalizable to online stores all over the world. This means that further research can implement a new sample method to measure in a more generalizable way.

As mentioned in the problem statement the security cycle consists of prevention, detection and reaction. This paper is mainly focused on prevention and detection. Further research can be conducted on the reaction phase of the cycle. For example when machine learning has access to open data sources with information on how companies dealt with cyberattacks, machine learning can provide a solution to an occurring cyberattack. Machine learning can compare the occurring attack with cyberattacks from the past and come up with a solution that suits the company best. Therefore, machine learning methods can ensure minimum involvement of humans in cyber security. In this, machine learning comes more or equally skilled as a human.

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- 6) What is your opinion about machine learning in cybersecurity?
- 7) In which way can machine learning be implemented in the processes of the company?

APPENDIX 1 - SURVEY

Hi,

This survey is for research on the cybersecurity of Dutch online stores. This research is conducted by four students of Tilburg University. The results will be used to write an academic paper. The survey is anonymised and completed within around 5 minutes. Thanks for responding!

- 1) Who is in the company responsible for cybersecurity? What is their function? What are the job requirements?
- 2) Are you aware of the consequences of a cyberattack and how they affect your company? If yes, what consequences?
- 3) Do you take any measurements against the cyberattacks? If yes, what kind of measurements? Do you invest in measurements?
- 4) Do you know how machine learning can improve cybersecurity and how to implement this?
- 5) Is the software monthly updated? What kind of software do you use?
- 6) How is the safety of customer information guaranteed?
- 7) How do you make your customers aware of phishing mails?

APPENDIX 2 - INTERVIEW

During the interview, questions that come up are also asked.

- 1) What is your function in the company?
- 2) Did the company experience cyberattacks in the past?
- 3) How did/would the company deal with cyberattacks?
- 4) What were the consequences of this cyberattack?
- 5) What do you know about machine learning?